

INTERNAL LOCUS OF CONTROL, ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT AND THE SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS OF G-10 STUDENTS

MANOAH GERAH O. CABILES

manoah.cabiles@deped.gov.ph

ORCID ID 0000-0001-5902-2958

Laguna Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus, Brgy. Del Remedio, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine whether significant relationship exists among the variables of internal locus of control, academic engagement and the science process skills of grade 10 students. This also attempted to determine the perceptions of the respondents to their internal locus of control as to the family origins and social class factors as well as the perceptions of the respondents to their academic engagement as to the behavioral, cognitive, and affective dimensions. Using a descriptive research design, it involved 100 grade 10 students enrolled in the modular distance and online distance learning modalities in San Jose National High School during the school year 2020-2021. Survey questionnaires and Science Process Skills test were used to measure their skills in terms of observing, classifying, measuring, communicating, inferring, and predicting. Results revealed that there is a significant relationship between the internal locus of control and the science process skills of the respondents particularly on the social class factor and the inferring skills. Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn. (1) There is a significant relationship between the internal locus of control and the science process skills of the respondents particularly on the Social Class factor and the Inferring skills, thus the null hypothesis is partially sustained. (2) There is no significant relationship between the affective dimension of Academic Engagement and the science process skills but there is significant relationship between the cognitive and behavioral dimensions of the academic engagement and the science process skills, thus the null hypothesis is partially sustained.

Keywords: (a) descriptive research design, (b) academic engagement, internal locus of control and science process skills, (c) survey questionnaires and teacher-made test, Pearson product moment correlation coefficient, mean and standard deviation, (d) Philippines/Southeast Asia